

SCOPING PAPER

CO₂-NEUTRAL GASES AND HYDROGEN

A NEFI Innovation Hub

NEFI – The Innovation Network for Industrial Transformation

NEFI – New Energy for Industry is an innovation network consisting of over 100 industry partners, 8 research partners, and 4 institutional partners. With 25 research and innovation projects dedicated to industrial transformation in Austria, an investment volume of nearly €100 million has been mobilised.

The goals of NEFI are:

- **Climate Neutrality** – Supplying selected sites with up to 100% renewable energy.
- **Value Creation and Location Security** – Promoting technology development and exports “Made in Austria”.
- **Industrial Resilience** – Ensuring energy supply, optimising processes, and improving infrastructure for Austrian industry.

The solutions developed within NEFI address 53% of the CO₂ emissions expected by 2040 and have the potential to generate an economic benefit of €2.2 billion. Additionally, by 2040, more than 25% of fossil energy imports could be avoided.

Achieving a climate-neutral industry by 2040 requires significant research and development efforts. Essential technologies are not yet fully developed, tested, or scalable to a sufficient extent. To bridge technological gaps and strategically drive innovations along realistic, scenario-based transformation pathways, six Innovation Hubs have been established.

NEFI Innovation Hubs

The NEFI Innovation Hubs are specialised networks led by renowned research institutions. Their goal is to initiate high-impact research and innovation projects that support the transition to a climate-neutral industry and position Austria as a technology leader in renewable energy and industrial innovation.

Both large corporations and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), as well as research institutions, are invited to participate in the Innovation Hubs.

NEFI Innovation Hubs: value proposition for partners

- ☑ Regular networking and information events: The NEFI Technology Talks present current technologies, trends, and developments.
- ☑ Support throughout the innovation process: From project idea to funding application and impact assessment.
- ☑ Dissemination of results: Effective communication and visibility.
- ☑ Access to state-of-the-art laboratory infrastructure.

The NEFI Innovation Hubs focus on the following key areas: CCUS, Circular Economy, CO₂-neutral Gases & Hydrogen, Electrification & Energy Efficiency, Flexibility, and Industrial Symbiosis. These topics have been identified as crucial for achieving industrial climate goals across different industries and scenarios ([NEFI Pathway to Industrial Decarbonisation](#) and [transform.industry - in German](#)).

1. CO₂-neutral Gases and Hydrogen – Current developments and trends

In times of climate change and the energy transition, CO₂-neutral gases and hydrogen are becoming increasingly important. They are considered key components for a sustainable energy supply and the defossilisation of various sectors.

Governments worldwide are promoting the use of CO₂-neutral gases and hydrogen through financial incentives and regulatory frameworks. In Austria, this includes the national hydrogen strategy as well as legal provisions such as the Environmental Promotion Act (UFG), the Renewable Energy Expansion Act (EAG), and the Gas Industry Act (GWG). Additionally, Austria is involved in European initiatives such as the IPCEI projects in the field of hydrogen.

The most relevant trends in the areas of CO₂-neutral gases and hydrogen are:

- (1) The growing importance of green hydrogen:** Green hydrogen is produced by electrolysis of water using renewable energy sources such as wind, solar, or hydropower. It is gaining increasing relevance as it is seen as a key technology for a climate-neutral energy future. Advances in electrolysis technology, economies of scale, and falling production costs are expected to contribute to making it economically competitive.
- (2) An increasing variety of CO₂-neutral gases:** In addition to hydrogen, other CO₂-neutral gases such as biogas, biomethane, synthetic methane (power-to-gas), ammonia, and synthetic fuels (power-to-liquid) are coming into focus. The development of these technologies is significantly influenced by political frameworks, technological advancements, and economic incentives.
- (3) Expansion of infrastructure:** To facilitate the use of hydrogen, increasing investments are being made in the development of suitable infrastructure for its storage and transport, such as pipelines or underground storage facilities. Additionally, the repurposing of existing natural gas networks for hydrogen transport is being explored.
- (4) Increased sector coupling through hydrogen:** Hydrogen is increasingly being used as an energy carrier to store surplus renewable electricity. The integration of hydrogen and other CO₂-neutral gases across various sectors—including industry (e.g., steel production), energy supply (e.g., seasonal storage), and mobility (e.g., fuel cell vehicles)—is growing.
- (5) The emergence of green markets:** With rising demand for CO₂-neutral energy carriers, new markets for green hydrogen and other climate-friendly gases are developing. These include trading systems for certified green hydrogen, guarantees of origin, and long-term supply agreements (Power Purchase Agreements, PPAs). Furthermore, the development of a European hydrogen market is progressing, supported by funding, standardisation, and regulatory measures.

2. High-Potential Technologies and Innovations in CO₂-neutral Gases and Hydrogen

Based on the general trends in the field of CO₂-neutral Gases and Hydrogen, the following high-potential technologies and innovations can be identified:

- (1) Green hydrogen through electrolysis:** Electrolysis enables the efficient and flexible production of green hydrogen, which can contribute to reducing CO₂ emissions in energy-intensive industries and the transport sector. Available technologies such as alkaline electrolysis (AEL) and proton exchange membrane electrolysis (PEM) can be scaled up and promoted for broader adoption. New approaches, including solid oxide electrolysis cells (SOEC) and anion exchange membrane electrolysis (AEM), are expanding the existing technology portfolio.
- (2) Power-to-X-technologies:** Power-to-X enables the conversion of surplus renewable electricity into hydrogen, methane, or synthetic fuels, providing a solution for seasonal energy storage. These technologies can be specifically utilised as flexibility options, supporting on-demand electricity generation and gas supply, thereby reducing dependence on fossil fuels in the transport, energy, and industrial sectors.
- (3) Injection of biomethane into the gas grid:** Using biogas from organic waste to produce biomethane is a quickly implementable and low-risk measure for CO₂ reduction. By upgrading it to natural gas quality, biomethane can be directly injected into the existing gas grid, allowing for straightforward implementation and rapid emission savings.
- (4) Hydrogen Storage Technologies:** Underground storage of hydrogen in geological formations offers a potentially cost-efficient solution for long-term energy storage. This is crucial for establishing a hydrogen-based energy supply, enabling the seasonal transfer of renewable energy from summer to winter and ensuring flexible utilisation according to demand.

3. Main Research Questions in the fields of CO₂-neutral Gases and Hydrogen

As part of the NEFI Innovation Hub for CO₂-neutral Gases and Hydrogen, projects will be developed to address the following research questions:

- How can the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of electrolysis and fuel cell technologies be further improved, particularly through the use of new materials?
- How can alternative hydrogen production methods, such as photocatalytic hydrogen production, methane pyrolysis, thermochemical hydrogen production, or biological processes, be scaled and commercialised?
- What new materials and technologies can improve the safe and efficient storage of hydrogen?
- What economic and technical challenges must be overcome to transport H₂ on a large scale (via pipelines, ships, or tankers)?
- How can Power-to-Gas and Power-to-Liquid technologies be further developed to improve efficiency and economic viability? How can their integration into the existing energy system be optimised?
- How can the integration of hydrogen into existing energy systems (e.g. electricity grid, gas grid) be technically and economically optimised? What technical and regulatory requirements must be met, and how can smart grids and digital technologies be utilised?
- What business models and market mechanisms promote the development and widespread adoption of H₂ and CO₂-neutral gases? What measures can enhance public acceptance and trust?
- How can the environmental impact of the entire hydrogen value chain (from production to utilisation) be minimised? How can negative environmental effects, such as water consumption and land use, be avoided in large-scale implementation?

4. Out-of-Scope Topics and Collaborative Overlaps

Through cooperation and alignment between the NEFI Innovation Hubs, synergies can be leveraged, technological trends identified, and innovations accelerated.

The NEFI Innovation Hub for CO₂-neutral Gases and Hydrogen expects overlaps with the following NEFI Innovation Hubs:

- CCUS: Blue hydrogen is produced through steam reforming of natural gas, with the resulting CO₂ being captured and stored (CCS). Additionally, CO₂ capture technologies enable its efficient conversion into valuable products such as synthetic fuels, chemicals, or building materials, contributing to the reduction of industrial emissions (CCU).
- Flexibility: PtX (Power-to-X) plants used for hydrogen production serve as a flexibility option, enabling effective sector coupling through key technologies such as electrolysis and fuel cells. They can absorb surplus energy, store it long-term, and feed it back into the system as needed.

5. Hub Co-Leads & Contact Persons

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